

DIRECTING THE YOUTH TO CRAFTS IN FOLK CRAFTS

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Abstract: This article presents the knowledge, skills and guidance needed to educate young people in craft entrepreneurship in national schools, and provides basic information and guidance on starting a business. In addition, a general description of the organization of small and private enterprises of handicraft enterprises is given. Information on network planning, interviews, organizers, demonstrations, practical exercises, business games, the use of innovative technologies and their use in the classroom is provided to develop the interests of young artisans.

Key words: Crafts, school, entrepreneur, technology, method, analysis, national, specialist, enterprise, property, product, talent, labor, craftsman, drought, fabric, learners, template, pattern, twin, stitching, evaluation, creative.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, our people had the opportunity to restore and develop their ancient national craft traditions. At the same time, increasing the technical support of handicraft production, improving the system of professional retraining of craftsmen, regulating their supply with raw materials, improving the quality of handicraft products in accordance with the market demand are among the urgent issues of today. Legal regulation of craft activities is one of the important tasks of the state. This is especially important for the transitional economy, which is developing new forms of economic management, including craft entrepreneurship.

In contrast to small and private enterprises, the following general characteristics of the organization of craft enterprises can be distinguished:

- belonging to a certain network;
 - practical combination of property and management in one person;
 - legal freedom;
 - small share in the product sales market;
 - creative description of the activity;
 - based on national traditions;
 - serving mainly the local market;
 - lack of a developed hierarchical structure of management;
 - not having a dominant position in the network;
- availability of state aid.

Craft entities can be organized in the form of small enterprises and private enterprises of various forms, or they can be individual entrepreneurs without forming a legal entity. That is, handicrafts are a part of small business entities, which are characterized by the preparation or provision of services in a small volume of labor products according to an individual order, in which the share of manual labor is large, and craftsmen creatively use their special

knowledge, skills and abilities. Usually, labor is not functionally and productively divided within a craft enterprise, and it is carried out on the basis of the ownership of the means of production by the craftsman-master. Also, the craftsman-master personally participates in the work process.

The development of craft entrepreneurship is important for any country, because this sector not only provides employment to the population, but also increases their well-being, brings out their existing abilities, and also helps to pass centuries-old national traditions and values from generation to generation.

Adolescence is a complex and, at the same time, important stage of development. During this period, mental, spiritual, anatomical and physiological changes are noticeable in the adolescent. It is appropriate to take into account its specific features when preparing teenagers for entrepreneurship in the family.

Name of the subject: Folk crafts and artistic design

The topic of the lesson: "Drought" art in folk crafts. Drawing and preparing a sketch for the "Quroq" garment to be sewn.

The duration of the training is 80 minutes

Objectives of the training: Educational: to give students a broad understanding of drought, to form practical skills about the preparation of food safety techniques and sanitary-hygiene rules.

Educational: to interest students in the art of carpentry, to develop their interest in technology, to educate them in the spirit of mutual respect and the formation of national and universal cultural values.

Developmental: to increase students' love for preserving our hard-earned independence, to continue the legacy and work of our ancestors, to direct them to the profession by forming the ability to be an example to young people;

Form of educational activity organization: Individual work

Teaching environment: Equipped auditorium

Teaching technology and methods. Conversation, "Why?" organizer, demonstrative, practical exercise.

Teaching aids: study guides, textbooks, computer, video projector, screen, slides, handouts, sewing machine, samples of dry goods, flowered and non-flowered materials, glue stick, iron, thread, needle, scissors, centimeter, tape.

Handouts: tests, technological maps, slides, instructions, handouts, crossword.

Training progress

II. Organizational part.

Greetings, determining the attendance of future artisans, inspecting the sanitary hygiene of workplaces and the equipped auditorium, introducing them to the plan.

Plan:

1. Understanding of dry goods.
2. Preparation of samples for sewing a pillow from dry.
3. Sewing a pillow from dry.

Students are asked activating questions

1. What are the types of dry matter?
2. How to prepare dry goods?
3. What should be paid attention to when sewing?

4. How many different types of dry are there?
5. What is the importance of kurak in an Uzbek household?

Answers will be heard by activating the future craftspeople and "Why?" they will be given a separate task to fill in the organizer and they will do it individually.

The answers of future artisans are listened to and the order of completing the task is checked. Provides guidance and recommendations. Didactic manuals, instructional maps, scientific literature, a cutting table, a blackboard, and didactic technical tools, necessary for the work of future artisans, will be held in the training workshop.

Through information and communication technologies and programs, the small pieces found in the sewing of various dry goods will explain to them the process of technological processing and describe the sequence of work to the future artisans.

In the development of entrepreneurship of young people, the future craftsman will demonstrate and show a video of making samples of dry goods through information and communication technologies and programs.

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